

RETAL

RETro propulsion Assisted Landing Technologies

AERODYNAMIC PHENOMENA OF RETRO PROPULSION DESCENT AND LANDING CONFIGURATIONS

FAR 2022 - HEILBRONN

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Overview

- Wind Tunnels at DLR in Cologne
- Configurations
- Trajectories and test conditions
- Wind Tunnel Test results:
 - Aerodynamic phase – TMK – RETALT1
 - Re-entry burn – H2K
 - Landing burn – VMK
 - Aerodynamic phase – TMK – RETALT2
- Conclusion and Outlook

Overview Wind Tunnels at DLR in Cologne

H2K (Hypersonic Wind Tunnel Cologne)

- Mach: 4.8 - 11.2
- Blow down facility (pressure-vacuum)

H2K – Test section

TMK (Trisonic Wind Tunnel Cologne)

- Mach: 0.5 – 4.5 (w/o ejector)
- Continuously adjustable Laval nozzle and diffuser

TMK – Test section

VMK (Vertical Free Jet Facility Cologne)

- Atmospheric free-jet facility
- $Ma = [0.4, 0.95], [1.5, 3.2]$

VMK – GOX/GH2 Test Stand Infrastructure

- Add-on to our Vertical Wind Tunnel (VMK)
- Plume of up to 115 bar and 3600 K stagnation conditions

Schematic of VMK

Schematic GOX/GH2 Test Stand

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RETALT1

- Two Stage To Orbit (TSTO) Vertical Take-off Vertical Landing (VTVL) RLV
- Payload capacity: 14t to Geostationary Transfer Orbit (GTO)
 - LOX/LH2 Gas Generator (GG) engines (similar to the Vulcain 2)
 - Stage 1: 9 engines
 - Stage 2: 1 engine (similar to first stage engine)
 - Stage 1 engines adapted to sea level conditions - 1179 kN Thrust (SL)
 - Stage 2 engine adapted to vacuum conditions - 1364 kN thrust (Vac)
 - Height: 103 m
 - Diameter: 6 m
 - Take-off Mass: 899 t
 - Retro propulsion and the novel aerodynamic control surfaces (interstage segment)

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 - Diameter: 6 m
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 - Retro propulsion and the novel aerodynamic control surfaces (interstage segment)

RETALT2

- Single Stage to Orbit (SSTO) Vertical Take-off Vertical Landing (VTVL) RLV
- Payload capacity: 0.5t to Low Earth Orbit (LEO)
 - LOX/LH2 engine (similar to Vinci) adapted to sea level conditions
 - 9 identical engines - 370 kN thrust (Vac)
 - More academically: „technology test bed“
 - Retro propulsion + novel aerodynamic control surfaces (fairing section)
 - Aerodynamic braking: capsule-like shape + fairing segments
 - Nozzle exits flush with base plane of the vehicle
 - Height: 17.6 m
 - Diameter: 7.4 m
 - Take-off Mass: 79.4 t

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RETALT1 return mission concept

* Graphic by DEIMOS

FAR2022 HEILBRONN - Aerodynamic Phenomena of Retro Propulsion Descent and Landing Configurations (RETALT)

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RETALT2 return mission concept

Scenario R2 DRL

* Graphic by DEIMOS

Trajectories and Test Conditions

RETALT1

RETALT2

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RETALT1 Wind Tunnel Model in TMK

Petals

Planar Fins

Grid Fins

RETALT1 Wind Tunnel Model in TMK

RETALT1 Wind Tunnel Model in H2K

Long Model

Short Model

RETALT1 Wind Tunnel Model

Nozzle segment with active nozzles

Tubular 4 components strain gauge balance

Model support sting

pSTAGE

Cylindrical segment

RETALT1 Wind Tunnel Model in VMK

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Flow conditions at aerodynamic control surfaces*

Assumptions:

- from blast wave analogy: $p_{ACS} = p_{\infty}$
 - Isentropic expansion
 - Weak shock system
- $p_{0,ACS} = p_{0,2}$

Mach number at ACS:

$$M_{ACS} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} M_{\infty}^2\right) (\gamma+1) M_{\infty}^2}{\left(1 + \frac{2\gamma}{\gamma+1} (M_{\infty}^2 - 1)\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} (2 + (\gamma-1) M_{\infty}^2)} - 1 \right)^{\frac{2}{\gamma-1}}}$$

Static pressure in dependence of angle of attack:

- Modified Newtonian law
- $C_p = C_{p_{max}} \sin^2 \alpha$; $C_{p_{max}} = \frac{p_{0,2} - p_{\infty}}{q_{\infty}}$

*Marwege, A. et al. : "Wind Tunnel Experiments of Interstage Segments used for Aerodynamic Control of Retro-Propulsion Assisted Landing Vehicles", CEAS Space J (2022).

Forces and Moments measured vs analytical

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RETALT1 Re-entry burn – 3 active engines H2K

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H2K

$T_{CC} = 300 \text{ K}$
 $C_T = 2.29 \pm 0.13$
 $M_\infty = 5.29$
 $p_0 = 4 \text{ bar}, T_0 = 450 \text{ K}$

Snapshot

Variance over 400 images

Variance over 10 images

Variance over 10 images

RETALT1 Re-entry burn – 3 active engines

H2K

Spectrograms of pressure sensors

- Dominant frequencies:
22.6 kHz, 21.9 kHz, 21.1 kHz, 2.5 kHz

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■ Wind Tunnel Test results:

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RETALT1 - Landing Burn VMK

- Example:
 - Run 28
 - $p_{CC} = 28 \text{ bar}$
 - $\frac{p_e}{p_\infty} = 0.49$
- fluctuations increase with increasing Mach numbers
- Largest fluctuations in stagnation region

RETALT1 - Landing Burn VMK

- Plume length linear dependent on momentum flux ratio and temperature ratio*:

- $$\frac{x}{D_e} = 3.1 \left(\frac{\rho_e u_e^2}{\rho_\infty u_\infty^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{T_{CC}}{T_e} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

- Factor 2.57 gives better fit for experiments

*Jarvinen, P. O.; Hill, A. F.: "Penetration of Retrorocket Exhausts into Subsonic Counterflows", Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets, Vol 10, 1973

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RETALT2 – Aerodynamic Phase TMK

RETALT2 in TMK at Mach 1.5, Petal deflection 45°

Conclusion

- Analytical approach for the design of aerodynamic control surfaces proposed
- Highly unsteady flow fields observed for retro propulsion environments for re-entry burn with 3 active engines and landing burn
- Dominant frequencies can be found in pressure measurements
- Plume length of landing burn follows analytical relation
- Aerodynamic Data Base (AEDB2.0) for RETALT1 and RETALT2 published on Zenodo (aerodynamic coefficients)

Outlook

- Further modal analyses planned for further understanding of unsteady phenomena and resulting loads
- Hot plume test being performed at the VMK at the moment
- CEAS Space Journal Special Issue will be published (a lot of papers already available online)

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COMPOSITES

THANK
YOU!

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THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 821890